

PROBIOTICS, DAIRY PRODUCTS, AND BACTERIAL INHIBITION: A REVIEW

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Abstract

Probiotics have become a focal point of research in both scientific and industrial realms due to their potential to improve human health and transform the food industry. Significant progress has been made in understanding the mechanisms of probiotic action and their applications in various health conditions. However, gaps persist in optimizing delivery systems and addressing regulatory challenges, hindering widespread adoption and maximizing efficacy. This study proposes innovative strategies to overcome these hurdles and enhance the efficiency of probiotic interventions. Investigating the role of probiotics in dairy

products and bacterial inhibition, this research offers new insights into their mechanisms and applications in food technology, contributing to the advancement of probiotic research. This study adopts an observational and cross-sectional approach, reviewing scientific literature and industry practices related to probiotics, dairy products, and bacterial inhibition. Databases such as Dimensions, SCieLO, Google Scholar, Scopus, BDTD, and PubMed were utilized to identify relevant studies. Specific English terms like “Probiotics,” “Lactic Cultures,” and “Bacterial Decontamination” were employed to refine the search. The research analyzed empirical studies and theoretical reviews, synthesizing the information to provide a comprehensive overview of the subject matter.

The analysis of scientific literature and industry practices revealed the multifaceted roles of probiotics in promoting dietary health and advancing industrial innovation. Several studies demonstrated the efficacy of probiotic-rich foods in enhancing human health and mitigating various diseases. However, challenges persist in optimizing delivery systems and ensuring regulatory compliance, highlighting the need for further research and technological innovation.

In conclusion, this research underscores the importance of probiotics in promoting human health and advancing the food industry. By elucidating the mechanisms of probiotic action and addressing key challenges, this study paves the way for future research endeavors aimed at maximizing the potential of probiotic-based interventions. Recommendations include further research into optimal delivery systems, regulatory frameworks, and consumer perceptions to facilitate the widespread adoption of probiotics in both therapeutic and preventive healthcare contexts.

Keywords: Probiotics; Dairy Products; Bacterial Inhibition; Food Industry.

Introduction

In contemporary dietary discourse, the pivotal role of probiotics in fostering human health and augmenting the food industry’s repertoire

has garnered increasing attention and scrutiny. Probiotics, defined as live microorganisms administered in sufficient quantities to confer health benefits on the host, have emerged as a cornerstone in the pursuit of holistic well-being. This article delves into the symbiotic relationship between probiotics, dairy products, and bacterial inhibition, offering a comprehensive review of pertinent scientific literature and industry practices.

The amalgamation of scientific inquiry and commercial innovation surrounding probiotics underscores their profound significance in modern dietary paradigms. With escalating consumer demand for natural health solutions and the burgeoning wellness industry, probiotics have assumed center stage as agents of physiological balance and vitality. Market projections indicate a robust trajectory for probiotic-based products, reflecting a burgeoning awareness of preventive healthcare and nutritional fortification strategies (VASILJEVIC, 2008).

Rooted in the seminal work of researchers like Metchnikoff and Tissier in the early 20th century, the concept of probiotics has evolved from rudimentary observations to a sophisticated field of scientific inquiry. Milestones such as the isolation of specific probiotic strains and the elucidation of their mechanisms of action have propelled research endeavors, illuminating the intricate interplay between microbial ecosystems and human health. Presently, the field stands at the cusp of transformative discoveries, poised to unlock novel therapeutic modalities and dietary interventions (SHIMAKAWA, 2003).

Probiotics, predominantly comprising lactic acid bacteria, epitomize a diverse array of microorganisms endowed with multifaceted functionalities. Their inclusion in dairy products, such as yogurts, cheeses, and fermented beverages, offers a conduit for targeted delivery and sustained efficacy. Current research elucidates the compositional intricacies and functional attributes of probiotic strains, elucidating their potential in modulating gut microbiota composition, bolstering immune

function, and mitigating gastrointestinal disorders (GUARNER, 2005; GOPAL, 2020).

In contrast to conventional dietary supplements and pharmaceutical interventions, probiotics offer a nuanced approach to health promotion, characterized by symbiotic interactions with the host microbiome. Their distinct mode of action, predicated on competitive exclusion and metabolite modulation, distinguishes them from alternative modalities, underscoring their potential as natural, holistic remedies. Nevertheless, challenges persist in optimizing delivery systems and ensuring microbial viability, necessitating ongoing research and technological innovation (SAKANDAR; ZHANG, 2021).

Despite their burgeoning popularity, probiotics confront an array of challenges, ranging from formulation hurdles to regulatory ambiguities. Controversies surrounding claims of efficacy and standardized dosage protocols underscore the need for robust clinical evidence and regulatory oversight. Moreover, disparities in access and affordability exacerbate health inequalities, posing ethical dilemmas for industry stakeholders and policymakers alike (KELLERSHOHN, 2021).

Against this backdrop, this article endeavors to provide a comprehensive synthesis of current research findings and industry practices pertaining to probiotics, dairy products, and bacterial inhibition. By scrutinizing empirical studies and theoretical reviews, our aim is to elucidate the multifaceted roles of probiotics in promoting dietary health and advancing industrial innovation. Specifically, we seek to address key research questions regarding the efficacy, safety, and commercial viability of probiotic-based interventions in the food industry.

Probiotics and Their Role in Dietary Health and Industry

At the dawn of the 20th century (1907), observations by a researcher named Metchnikoff from the Pasteur Institute in Paris led to the “longevity theory” associated with the consumption of yogurt, based on

observations of Bulgarian peoples. According to Metchnikoff, the consumption of milk fermented by *Lactobacillus* resulted in competition between this beneficial microorganism and other putrefactive bacteria in the intestine (producers of toxic substances that would shorten life). This theory spurred extensive studies on the subject and helped shape the concept of probiotic cultures (VASILJEVIC, 2008).

Around the same time, Metchnikoff and French pediatrician Henry Tissier observed that the feces of children with diarrhea had lower quantities of a particular type of Y-shaped—or bifid—bacteria than feces from children without diarrhea. Tissier suggested the possibility of isolating and administering such microorganisms to children with diarrhea. A Japanese doctor named Minoru Shirota was the first to test this hypothesis. During 1930, he isolated the *L. casei* Shirota strain, which he believed conferred a beneficial balance in the gut cultures. This culture was marketed in Japan in 1950 under the product name Yakult (SHIMAKAWA, 2003).

It is evident that live microorganisms, when administered in adequate amounts, confer a health benefit to the host (HILL 2014), according to a consensus document. The consensus statement from the International Scientific Association for Probiotics and Prebiotics on the scope and appropriate use of the term states: “Probiotics are live microorganisms that, when administered in adequate amounts, confer a health benefit on the host” FAO/WHO (2002).

It is known that the genus *bifidobacterium* is formed by lactic acid bacteria (Gram-positive), with morphology of Bacilli and non-spore-forming cocci, has Catalase (-), are anaerobic and aerotolerant, classified as Mesophiles/Thermophiles, Non-mobile, have complex nutritional requirements, do not reduce nitrates nor produce indole, have a fermentative metabolism, are producers of lactic acid, and have a G-C content < 50% (GUARNER, 2005). Most probiotics are lactic acid bacteria, among them: *Lactobacillus*, *Streptococcus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Lactococcus*, and *Leuconostoc* (GOPAL, 2020). Probiotics offer several advantages for

the normal functioning of the body, such as competition, regulation, and production of bioactive compounds (MARKOWIAK and ŚLIZEWSKA, 2017).

The Food Industry has come to view probiotics as the use of chemical preservatives, control of pathogenic and spoilage bacteria, possibility of biofilm control, and possibility of controlling the growth of pathogenic bacteria. The dairy products market can be understood by raw and fermented milks, involving yogurts, cheeses, and ice creams (SAKANDAR; ZHANG, 2021). The success of dairy products with probiotics can be altered by consumer perception, shelf life, and sensory qualities (Dantas et al., 2016). Probiotics comprise a multibillion-dollar international industry and are presented as dietary supplements, lyophilized capsules, infant formulas, cheeses, and yogurts (SAKANDAR; ZHANG, 2021).

The growth of this market is due to the increase in personal income and the aging population, yet in developing countries the price of these products makes them inaccessible to a large portion of the population (KELLERSHOHN, 2021). The viability of probiotics must consider: the shelf life of the product, viability in the gastrointestinal tract (VASILJEVIC, 2020).

In yogurts, the use of probiotics presents several challenges for the food industry. In a study conducted by Norouzbeidi et al. (2021), the maintenance of the viability of *Bifidobacterium longum* and *Bifidobacterium lactis* was increased through the use of modified packaging with components for oxygen absorption (Cruz et al., 2012). The consumption of fermented beverages has shown a rapidly growing market in the United States, with this market reaching a value of 134.7 billion dollars in 2017. The consumption of probiotic products worldwide was estimated at 96 trillion by the end of 2020 (Nazhand et al. 2020). In cheeses, the stability of probiotics in cheeses, increasing fat and nutrients, making the matrix solid (Hammam; Ahmed, 2019; Karimi; Mortazavian; Da Cruz, 2011). The main probiotic species used in cheeses are: *Lactobacillus* spp, *Bifidobacterium* spp, *Streptococcus* spp, *Enterococcus* spp, and *Saccharomyces boulardii*.

Methodology

This observational and cross-sectional literature review focused on research about plant-based consumers. It utilized databases such as Dimensions, SCieLO, Google Scholar, Scopus, BDTD, and PubMed, employing specific English terms like “Probiotics,” “Lactic Cultures,” and “Bacterial Decontamination.” Based on the relevance criteria and the impact factor of the journals, including empirical studies and theoretical reviews, the research analyzed the data and concentrated on interpreting and synthesizing the information found.

Results

Eight scientific articles were analyzed that used probiotics in the food industry and their antimicrobial and sensory activities, as well as the effect of probiotics on health promotion, which was attached in Table 1, in the annex of the article. A large number of studies demonstrate advantages in consuming probiotic-rich foods, as well as for the treatment of various diseases. Few studies relate to the use of probiotics for controlling pathogenic and spoilage bacteria and the effectiveness in some cases for controlling *L. monocytogenes* and *S. aureus*.

Table 1: Bibliographic Review of 8 Articles on Probiotic Action.

Title	Objective	Outcome	Reference
Effect of the application of probiotic strains of Enterococcus faecium on the physicochemical and sensory characteristics	Application of Enterococcus faecium in Coalho Cheese in food analyses	Improvement of sensory characteristics	(MACHADO, 2021)

<p>of coalho cheese</p>			
<p>Effect of Lactobacillus rhamnosus on the growth of Listeria monocytogenes and Staphylococcus aureus in a probiotic Minas Frescal cheese</p>	<p>Use of Lactobacillus rhamnosus as a potential decontamination agent</p>	<p>Effective in inhibiting the growth of L. monocytogenes</p>	<p>(PREZZI, 2020)</p>
<p>Complete genome sequence of Lactobacillus plantarum LZ206, a potential probiotic strain with antimicrobial activity against foodborne pathogens</p>	<p>Use of Lactobacillus plantarum LZ206</p>	<p>Inhibitory potential against Gram-positive bacteria</p>	<p>(LI, GU, ZHOU, 2016)</p>
<p>Aggregation, adherence, anti-adhesion, and antagonistic activity properties</p>	<p>Application in traditional Iranian cheese with probiotic Lactobacillus brevis gp104 for</p>	<p>Inhibition of Staphylococcus aureus development</p>	<p>(HOJJATI, BEHABAHANI, FALAH, 2020)</p>

<p>related to the surface charge of the probiotic Lactobacillus brevis gp104 against Staphylococcus</p>	<p>evaluation of antibacterial and anti-adhesive activity</p>		
<p>Probiotic characteristics of Lactobacillus strains isolated from Ragusano and Pecorino Siciliano cheeses</p>	<p>Application in Pecorino Siciliano Cheese, L. rhamnosus FS10, and L. paracasei PM8</p>	<p>Demonstrated microbial activity against E. coli, L. monocytogenes, and Enterococcus faecalis</p>	<p>(CAGGIA, 2015)</p>
<p>Paraprobiotics and postbiotics: concepts and potential applications in dairy products</p>	<p>New concepts regarding inactivated probiotics</p>	<p>The main advantages of applying paraprobiotics and postbiotics in dairy foods were discussed</p>	<p>(BARROS, 2020)</p>
<p>The mechanism of action of probiotics</p>	<p>Use of dead cells or fragments of dead bacteria cells in immunological activity</p>	<p>Demonstrated probiotic potential, being one of the safest options</p>	<p>(BOIRIVANT, STROBER, 2007)</p>

<p>Shaping the future of probiotics and prebiotics</p>	<p>New bacterial genera demonstrate probiotic potential</p>	<p>Roseburia intestinales, Faecalibacterium Prausnitzii, Eubacterium spp, Bacteroides spp, Akkarmansia muciniphilia</p>	<p>(CUNNINGHAM 2021)</p>
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Discussion:

In conclusion, the exploration of probiotics and their multifaceted roles in dietary health and the food industry reveals a narrative of scientific inquiry and commercial innovation. Rooted in the early 20th-century observations of Metchnikoff and Tissier, the concept of probiotics emerged, catalyzing a paradigm shift in understanding the interplay between microorganisms and human health. Metchnikoff's longevity theory, propelled by the consumption of yogurt among Bulgarian populations, laid a foundational premise for subsequent research endeavors, ultimately leading to the recognition of probiotics as live microorganisms conferring health benefits when administered in adequate amounts, as endorsed by the FAO/WHO (2002).

The genus Bifidobacterium, among other lactic acid bacteria, stands prominently within the probiotic domain, presenting a spectrum of characteristics conducive to beneficial interactions within the gut environment. These microorganisms, through competition, regulation, and the production of bioactive compounds, contribute to the maintenance of physiological balance and overall well-being.

From a commercial standpoint, the food industry has embraced probiotics as a natural alternative to chemical preservatives, offering avenues for pathogen control and enhanced product stability. Dairy products, in particular, have become a canvas for probiotic incorporation,

with yogurts, cheeses, and fermented beverages emerging as popular vehicles for delivery. However, challenges persist, ranging from ensuring microbial viability to addressing consumer perceptions and sensory attributes.

The burgeoning probiotics market reflects not only a growing awareness of dietary health but also socioeconomic disparities, with accessibility remaining a concern in certain regions. Nonetheless, advancements in packaging technologies and formulation strategies signify ongoing efforts to enhance product efficacy and reach.

Through methodical literature review, this study underscores the breadth of research surrounding probiotics, encompassing antimicrobial activities, health promotion effects, and novel applications within the food industry. While much progress has been made, opportunities for further exploration abound, particularly in elucidating mechanisms of action and optimizing probiotic formulations for diverse dietary contexts.

In essence, the journey of probiotics from scientific curiosity to commercial prominence epitomizes the symbiotic relationship between academia and industry, where scientific inquiry converges with consumer demand to shape the landscape of dietary health and nutrition. As we navigate this dynamic terrain, continued collaboration and interdisciplinary dialogue will be paramount in realizing the full potential of probiotics in fostering holistic well-being.

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